

Performance and Safety of Li/MnO₂ Pouch Cell Batteries

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ABSTRACT

The US Army Communications and Electronics Command (CECOM) is developing high capacity primary Li/MnO₂ pouch cell batteries as man-portable power sources for the individual soldier. Flat wound prismatic configurations with laminated foil enclosures provide efficient utilization of available battery box space. This technology can deliver 16 Ah in cells that will replace 7 Ah Li/SO₂ D cells in the Army BA-X47 two cell battery pack. This paper presents performance and safety results of this developing technology in Army battery configurations and applications.

Introduction

The need for information on the battlefield has increased the amount of electronic technology carried by the dismounted soldier. Today's soldier carries a wide selection of electronic devices such as computers, global positioning systems, communication radios, bio-sensors, thermal imaging devices, and advanced weapons systems. This array of power hungry devices is placing demands on existing battery technologies to deliver more energy in smaller, lighter batteries.

Li/MnO₂ pouch cell batteries have demonstrated significant increases in power and energy capability compared to existing cylindrical cell Li/SO₂ batteries, and modest increases compared to cylindrical cell Li/MnO₂ batteries. Two high profile applications for which these batteries are being developed are Land Warrior (LW) and Thermal Weapon Site (TWS). Both systems currently use either a 6V, primary, two D cell Li/SO₂ battery (BA-5847) or a 8V, rechargeable battery packaged with six lithium-ion 18650 cells (BB-2847). These batteries cannot power these devices for sufficient mission times to make them viable on a battlefield or cost effective in a training environment. A larger 12V/24V BA-X90 pouch cell battery is also being developed for SINCGARS radios. The X90 battery configuration is the most widely used battery in the Army inventory.

The Army is working with BlueStar Advanced Technology Corporation, Vancouver, BC, Ultralife Batteries Inc., Newark, NY and Hawker Eternacell Inc., Elmwood Park, NJ to develop their Li/MnO₂ chemistries into pouch cells for Army batteries (1-6).

Cell and Battery Design

All the pouch cells are comprised of the same basic components regardless of the cell size or manufacturer. The anode is lithium metal with a copper current collector and nickel tab. The cathode active material is either chemically or electrolytically synthesized manganese dioxide. A high surface area carbon is added to the active material and Teflon is used as a binder. Aluminum or stainless steel are used as the cathode current collector and tab. Celgard 2400 or 2300 (fusible) separators are used. Some typical electrolyte formulations are LiClO₄ in a ternary mixture of dimethoxyethane (DME), tetrahydrofuran (THF), and propylene carbonate (PC) or Li-imide in DME, PC and dioxalane (DOL) or Li-triflate in DME, PC and ethylene carbonate (EC).

The cell configuration is a multi-wrap pseudo-elliptical winding. This wrap is sealed in a laminated metallized foil pouch, that forms a barrier to oxygen, water vapor and the electrolyte solvents. The pouch materials typically consist of some combination of low density polyethylene (LDPE), Suryln®, polyester, and aluminum. Heat sealing under pressure is used to close the cell.

A drawing of the BA-5347 pouch cell battery is shown in Figure 1. It is a 5V nominal battery that is 2.55Lx1.5Wx3.75H inches and weighs 0.7 pounds. It contains a state of charge indicator (SOC) with LED's, a complete discharge device (CDD) to react all of the lithium for safe disposal, a diode to prevent charging, a thermal fuse (93°C), a fast blow electrical fuse (5A), and dual connectors for various applications.

Figure 1. Schematic of BA-5347 Pouch Cell Battery
(BlueStar Advanced Technology Corp.)

Experimental Testing

Performance testing was performed in-house on 135 Li/MnO₂ BA-5347 pouch cell batteries. An additional 150 of these batteries were sent to Army users for field testing in equipment. Constant current discharges between 0.25A and 5A to 0 volts and constant power discharges at 18W were performed at -30°C, 25°C and 55°C. Duty cycles were prepared for the Thermal Weapons Site (TWS) and the Land Warrior (LW) applications:

TWS: -30°C 8W for 2 minutes; then 5W to 4V
 25°C 9W for 2 minutes; then 6.5W to 4V
 55°C 12W for 2 minutes; then 9W to 4V

LW: All temperatures - 3A for 1.6 minutes, then
 2A for 4.3 minutes, then
 1A for 2.5 minutes, then
 0.5A for 1.6 minutes,
 Repeat until 4V is reached.

Fifteen batteries were stored for 28 days at 55°C and discharged the TWS and LW duty cycles and 18W continuous.

Safety tests were performed and video taped on cells and batteries at the manufacturers facilities witnessed by Army representatives. The tests included the following:

- External Short Circuit - 30 ohm resistor
- Crush - 6mm round bar

- Nail Penetration - 2/3 and full cell thickness
- Bullet Penetration - 22 caliber bullet
- Charging - 100mA and 3A, fresh and 50% discharged cell
- Forced Overdischarge - UL1642 at 3A
- Oven Exposure - 3hrs at 120°C

Results and Discussion

The most important reason why the Army is interested in developing this primary battery technology is clearly demonstrated in Figure 2. The pouch cell Li/MnO₂ in a BA-5347 Army battery has twice the capacity of Li/SO₂. Figure 2 also shows that the Li/MnO₂ chemistry can handle the high initial power load (for some equipment applications, like the TWS) better than Li/SO₂.

Figure 2. Comparison of BA-5347 Battery Chemistries

The average discharge capacities performed at constant currents and 18W constant power are listed in Table 1. The pouch cell battery demonstrated excellent rate capability by achieving over 13Ah of capacity at 4A (25°C). Little or no capacity was observed above 4 volts at -30°C, but the batteries did achieve over 8Ah to 3.5 volts. The battery electronics lower the operating voltage of the battery 0.5 to 0.8 volts depending on the discharge rate. This voltage loss is seen in Figure 3 where a complete battery and two pouch cells in series were discharged at the same conditions. This is an area that possible improvements are being investigated.

Table 1. Average BA-5347 Battery Capacities.

Temp. (°C)	Discharge Rate (A)	Avg. Capacity @ 4V (AH)	Avg. Capacity @ 3.5V (AH)
25	0.25	16.1	16.5
	0.5	15.1	15.6
	1	15.1	15.6
	2	14.3	14.9
	3	13.9	14.6
	4	13.5	14.1
	5	7.0	Fuse opened
	18W	11.1	-
55	0.25	16.7	17.3
	0.5	15.5	16.3
	1	15.4	16.1
	2	13.8	14.9
	3	13.0	13.5
	4	11.5	Fuse opened
	5	11.5	Fuse opened
	18W	11.5	Fuse opened
-30	0.25	10.8	12.3
	0.5	8.2	10.3
	1	3.9	7.0
	2	0.1	8.2
	3	0.04	8.7
	4	-	8.7
	5	-	8.5
	18W	Fuse opened	Fuse opened

Figure 3. Effect of Battery Electronics on Voltage

In the LW and TWS duty cycles at 25°C and 55°C, the Li/MnO₂ pouch cell battery delivers capacities (Table 2) that give the soldier twice the mission time of the equivalent Li/SO₂ primary battery and close to three times the mission time of the rechargeable lithium-ion Army battery. At -30°C to a 4V cutoff the pouch cell delivers only slightly better capacity than the Li/SO₂.

Table 2. BA-5347 Capacities in TWS and LW

Duty Cycle	Temp. (°C)	Avg. Capacity @ 4V (AH)
TWS	25	14.2
	55	13.6
	-30	4.0
LW	25	14.5
	55	13.9
	-30	4.8

A limited amount of storage data was collected and is shown in Table 3. The results indicate the batteries have high temperature storage limitations. Comparisons of these capacities with those in Tables 2 show that only 50% of the non-storage capacity was attained. This result leads to the question of the shelf-life of the pouch cell enclosure, since Li/MnO₂ battery chemistry is very stable with only a 1% annual capacity loss (7).

Table 3. Capacities After 28 Days Storage at 55°C

Temp. (°C)	Test	Capacity @ 4V (AH)
25	18W	1.5 avg (1)
	TWS	6.5
		2.6
		6.8
	LW	6.7
2.2		
55	18W	2.2 avg (2)

- (1) 1 of 5 tested leaked.
- (2) 2 of 5 fuses opened. (at 3.8V and 4.1V)

The safety results in Table 4 indicate that overall, this battery technology is safe. All safety test reactions were orders of magnitude less severe than the violent ventings of Li/SO₂ cells. Li/MnO₂ pouch cells and batteries subjected to electrical abuse experienced frequent mild ventings (pouch cell

Table 4. Safety Testing Results

Test	Variations	Result
External Short Circuit	Cell	Safe, vent opened at anode tab, $I_{max}=45A$, $T_{max}=70^{\circ}C$
	Battery w/electronics	Fuse opened within 5 seconds
	Battery, no electronics	Safe, $I_{max}=70A$, $T_{max}=115^{\circ}C$
Crush		Safe, no flame, audible venting
Nail Penetration	Slow, 2/3	Safe, no flame
	Slow, full	Safe, no flame, discharged 9.9Ah at 3A
	Fast, 2/3	Safe, no flame, audible venting
	Fast, full	Safe, audible venting, flash and unsustained flame
Bullet Penetration	Cell	Safe, flash and unsustained flame, discharged 60% at 3A
	Battery, 2 bullets	Safe, flash and unsustained flame
	Battery, 3 bullets	Flash and flame
Charge	Fresh, 100mA	Safe, $T_{max}=35^{\circ}C$
	Fresh, 3A	Safe, $T_{max}=70^{\circ}C$
	50%, 100mA	Safe, $T_{max}=27^{\circ}C$
	50%, 3A	Safe, $T_{max}=70^{\circ}C$
Forced Over Discharge		Safe, $T_{max}=100^{\circ}C$
Over Exposure		Safe, vented

burping) and electrolyte leakage. The standard safety features of the BA-5347 battery minimize the probability of external shorts, cell reversal, and charging of the battery. When abused mechanically, venting is frequent and sparks are probable, but no violent venting occurs. Explosions and violent ventings are improbable due to the pouch cell enclosure opening before a significant build-up a pressure occurs.

Developmental areas of this battery technology that still need to be addressed in more detail include reducing the voltage loss due to the battery electronics, high temperature storage, shelf-life, and acquiring more safety data to provide statistical significance.

Conclusions

Primary Li/SO₂ has been considered the best the Army could hope for in terms of energy for man-portable communication and electronic equipment for many years. From the performance and safety results presented here, the Army believes that the Li/MnO₂ pouch cell battery technology will offer a significant improvement over Li/SO₂.

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